

Development of an Electrophoresis Machine for Rapid Genotype Analysis

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ABSTRACT

The diverse use of electrophoretic technologies is frequent for both chemical and biological processes having a significant in learning and interaction with biological binding patterns, such as specification, physicochemical characteristics, redox states, and ligand exchange. The advancements in the modeling of electrophoresis systems with the capacity to simultaneously evaluate three samples, with a smart alarming system to indicate a complete procedure would be fabricated. Due to the two-way nature of the fluid-structure interaction, the deformation of the particles is with a sizable impact on the flow field surrounding them. Up until now, only electrophoresis of either hard particles or soft particles without cores has addressed the challenge of a rapid test for genotype. The developed device comprises of 1.5KW transformer, a regulator, a timer relay, and an alarm system. The produced device is capable of evaluating the genotype in humans by using blood as a sample under electric current within a few minutes. The device contains three tank outputs instead of the conventional two tanks with a capacity to evaluate three samples simultaneously, embedded in the control is a mechanism for monitoring and visualization genotyping. The developed device allows for multiple gels to be stacked in the tank, whereby it can analyze 30-60 samples. The developed Electrophoresis device allows analysis of size and charge, parameters inaccessible to liquid-phase methods: thus, genotyping size patterns, variable length repeats, and haplotypes are possible, as well as adaptability to typing of point variations using protocols that create a difference detectable by the electrophoresis device.

Keywords: Electrophoresis, Polyacrylamide, Analytical Operation and Genotype.

1 Introduction

Chemical and biological processes at the interface of these domains are frequently better understood because of the widespread use of electrophoretic technologies in these disciplines [1]. To learn about significant interactions between metal centers and biological binding partners, such as speciation, physicochemical characteristics, redox states, and ligand exchange, biological inorganic chemistry heavily relies on a novel and cutting-edge methodologies. The nature of these interactions frequently dictates the

biological characteristics of metal-biomolecule conjugates and enables us to comprehend how metal species operate [1].

One of the laboratory methods used to separate RNA, protein, or DNA molecules depending on their electric charge and size is called electrophoresis (the word electrophoresis means "to bear electrons"). The molecules are propelled through a gel by an electric current. The gel's pores function as a filter, allowing smaller molecules to pass more quickly than bigger ones. Through the gel, it divides the molecular fragments into bits. Additionally, it divides liquid-state molecules. It is a well-known method of biomolecule analysis in the fields of molecular biology and biochemistry. Because a cell's DNA is too lengthy to fit into the gel's well, restriction enzymes must first break it down before it can be placed into the gel. Electrophoresis can be used to validate some diagnoses whereas when DNA or proteins are altered, they become shorter or longer and behave differently during electrophoresis than they would under normal circumstances.

In labs for the chemical and biological sciences as well as in microfluidic systems, the electrophoresis phenomenon is employed to regulate the transit of species and particles. In the future decades, the global prevalence of chronic diseases including cancer, infectious diseases, and genetic abnormalities is predicted to rise, which will be a major driver for the expansion of the electrophoresis market. Another factor anticipated to fuel the expansion of the target market is the rising demand among various research and development organizations for the electrophoretic separation of cancer proteins [2]. Additionally, the examination of the electrophoresis process in the actual world would be aided by the modeling that forecasts the electrophoretic behavior of soft particles. Indeed, such computer models can aid in the development of electrophoresis technologies. However, it appears that the advancements in the modeling of electrophoresis systems have not been accomplished by a single researcher or scientist [2].

An analytical method called electrophoresis has been used to separate complicated mixtures of DNA, proteins, and other chemical or biological species [3]. The genotype of a human individual is essentially represented by the letters AA, AS, and SS, and is detected using electrophoresis equipment [4]. Since more than a century ago, scientists have understood that materials like proteins and enzymes may move in an electric field. However, it wasn't until the late 1930s, when Arne Tiselius showed that electrophoresis could be used for the separation of serum proteins, that this phenomenon was used for common chemical separations. The method performed by Tiselius was the first instance in which electrophoresis was utilized for clinical examination, as was later acknowledged by the 1948 Nobel Prize in Chemistry. To conduct these tests, Tiselius employed a running buffer and a U-shaped tube into which he put his material. The proteins in the sample started to split according to their charge and size as they moved toward the electrode with the opposing charge when an electric field was generated across this tube. The outcome was a set of wide, only partially resolved bands, which were subsequently utilized to analyze the sample's protein composition.

Charged particles such as proteins, bacteria, and other inorganic objects have all been distinguished using electrophoresis. Additionally, it is used to describe the zeta potential surface charge characteristics [5]. However, slip velocity develops at the particle surface for particles formed of hydrophobic materials or coated by these materials, reducing the mobility of the particles. If one ignores the slip coefficient while interpreting the mobility data, one will therefore obtain an incorrectly inflated value of the zeta potential.

Because Tiselius' technique resulted in a series of changing boundaries between areas containing various protein mixes, it is now known as "moving boundary electrophoresis." Using smaller amounts of material that will enable analytes to be separated into tight bands or zones and more effective separation equipment are more typical in modern laboratories. These circumstances lead to a generic methodology that is now referred to as "zone electrophoresis." Many scientists enhanced and developed the answers throughout time by taking into consideration the impacts of different important factors after initially modeling electrophoresis difficulties for very particular and basic modes. The governing equations of electrophoresis cannot yet be solved analytically (at least not for the most common situations), and the analytical formulas that are now available are the products of several simplifications and are only applicable under specific circumstances. At the same time, it appears that the findings of each researcher looking into this process may be seen as stepping stones that provide the groundwork for future developments. The accomplishments will also give scientists and engineers the required instructions for creating and constructing microscopic systems based on capillary electrophoresis [2]. When it comes to the modeling of soft particle electrophoresis, there are still certain research gaps. For instance, discussions about concentrated suspensions are only possible using the outdated traditional cell model. Based on the first-order perturbation analysis, the equations are analytically solved. However, the surface adsorption of particles on the border, particle mobility in regions other than the channel axis, and particle interaction in the microchannel have not yet been studied in capillary electrophoresis models. Recent research suggests that some bio-species cores may be deemed electrolyte permeable. Electrophoretic mobility might rise as a result of such a factor. There is still a great deal of work to be done [6]. The modeling of reactive electrophoresis, which involves electrophoresis and a chemical reaction occurring concurrently [7], [8], has also been unexpectedly underappreciated. Particle deformation is yet another lately brought up topic of attention by a few researchers. As a result of electric force, hydrodynamic drag, or fluid structural interaction, which is a recent field of study on the particle electrophoresis that impacts the particle inertia, development of EDL, and subsequent distributions of the charge throughout the particle, the particle may deform in reality [9]. Due to the two-way nature of the fluid-structure interaction, the deformation of the particles has a sizable impact on the flow field surrounding them [6]. Up to now, only electrophoresis of either hard particles or soft particles without cores has addressed this new challenge [7], [9]. Capillary electrophoresis-mass spectrometry (CE-MS) has seen increased interest in recent years due to developments in mass spectrometry (MS) technology as well as the demand for separation methods with high speed and resolving power. Interface advancements have increased the CE-MS technologies' robustness and repeatability, enabling extremely confident characterization and identification of peptides, cellular proteins, PTMs, and protein complexes. These upgrades have also improved sensitivity, enabling the use of CE on complicated samples with low concentrations [10]. Despite being more susceptible to technical faults and difficulties than liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS), CE-MS has, in some situations, outperformed traditional LC-based procedures because of advancements in equipment (e.g., separation of intact proteins and protein complexes). Sheath-less and sheath-liquid interfaces may both be used to obtain very sensitive ionization efficiency at a lower flow rate (in the separation capillary) than LC, which lowers background noise and improves MS detectability [10]. Modern single-shot CZE-ESI MS and neutrally coated capillaries (1 m) have significantly increased the peak performance of CE-MS techniques in proteomics research. However, no one dimension can completely reduce sample complexity. Instead, the best method for raising peak capacity and lowering

sample complexity is to use multidimensional separations. The main limitation of CE is sample loading, which may be overcome using straightforward techniques as shown in top-down and bottom-up applications [11], [12]. Very few articles over the past few years have discussed the use of CE-MS for quantitative proteomics, TDMS, and native MS. MS and cross-linking have been utilized successfully to examine protein structure, although there aren't many cross-linking findings using CE-MS. The Dovichi group is driving technical development with the aim that CE-MS will be employed in proteomics research as frequently as LC-MS [10]. Since CE works well for native separations, native MS will increasingly be used to examine protein dynamics and conformation. While native MS offers in-depth details on protein subunit configurations via non-covalent interactions, TDMS can provide structural information of proteins covalently bound to other proteins in addition to a complete proteoform characterization. These distinct characteristics imply that TDMS and native MS can be complimentary at various levels and can be used to offer thorough protein structural knowledge. These MS-based techniques will work well together, and it will be beneficial for both structural biology and proteomics research [10]. A charged colloidal particle submerged in an electrolyte solution moves in relation to the electrolyte solution when the particle is exposed to an external electric field. This process, known as electrophoresis, is used to separate macromolecules like proteins and characterize the characteristics of surface charges.

To distinguish between different-sized proteins that are charged in aqueous solutions due to amino acids, electrophoresis has frequently been utilized. Charged groups resembling amino acids can also be used to explain the surface charge on microorganisms. On the other side, the lattice flaws are connected to the mechanism for a charge on crystalline inorganic materials. Long-term investigations on the electrophoretic motion of stiff particles in aqueous electrolyte solutions have involved meticulous mathematical analysis carried out under the presumption of nonslip boundary conditions at the particle surface [5]. In the current study, we take into account for the first time the electrophoretic motion of a stiff nonconducting spherical particle with a Navier velocity slip. Since there have been several attempts to coat micro and nanoparticles with silica or polymers to change their conductivity, optical characteristics, and reactivities recently [13], velocity slip at the particle surface still exists. Electrophoresis is one technique for characterizing these particles. In the past, electrophoretic mobility measurements have been used to characterize the surface charge characteristics of particles [5]. However, velocity slip happens near the surface of these hydrophobic polymeric materials since they are often hydrophobic [14]. The mobility of these polymer-coated particles under an externally applied electric field is influenced by both the velocity slip at the particle surface as well as the surface charge or zeta potential. Therefore, using electromobility to calculate a particle's zeta potential or surface charge leads to inaccurate conclusions [5]. When the zeta potential for a particle with a hydrophobic surface is estimated from electrophoretic mobility measurements without taking velocity slip into account, the estimated zeta potential will be significantly higher than the actual one, deceiving the surface charge characteristics of the particle. It is vital to measure these two aspects of the particle independently because the zeta potential describes the surface charge of the particle while the velocity slip reveals the wettability of the surface. By adjusting the pH or the buffer concentration, one may regulate the zeta potential, and by introducing surfactants, one can change the velocity slip or the hydrophobicity [5]. Analytical research has been done on the electrophoresis of core-shell composite soft particles having a hydrophobic inner core and a highly charged polyelectrolyte layer (PEL) [15]. The continuity equation may be used to describe the

movement of components in liquid media under the effect of an applied electric field [16]. It represents a nonlinear conservation rule that can be solved numerically in both time and space and is based on the balancing laws of continuous transport systems. For exploring the fundamentals of electrokinetic separations and offering insights into the behavior of buffer systems and sample components of all electrophoretic separation techniques, such as moving boundary electrophoresis, CZE, CGE, ITP, IEF, EKC, ACE, and CEC, dynamic models are the most flexible tools available [16]. The dynamic simulators are the most adaptable instruments for investigating the foundations of electrokinetic separations since they can foretell the movement of ions in solution under the impact of an electric field [16]. Over the 2010–2020 decade, there has been a substantial advancement in the state of dynamic computer simulation software and its application. The three most popular simulators and the original 2D model were expanded throughout the time period under consideration, and additional one- and multi-dimensional models were created [16]. The development of computation methods that enable faster simulations (like SIMUL6 and SPYCE) and easier access to multidimensional simulations was prioritized. New features were also made available, such as the incorporation of complexation for the simulation of chiral separations and the departure from electroneutrality for the simulation of electrophoresis in nanochannels.

Mass capillary electrophoresis (MCE) has been widely used for biochemical analysis due to its benefits over conventional experimental setup, including minimal reagent use, quick analysis, high throughput, high integration capacity, and decreased labor effort [17]. Optical detection in electrophoresis technology offers several appealing qualities like a rapid signal response, high sensitivity, and simple operation. Electrochemical detection offers benefits over optical methods due to the relative lack of electroactive pollutants and environmental insensitivity to prevent the flaw of possible background signals [17]. A potent tool for microscale analytical, micropreparative, and (macro)preparative separations of biomolecules and bioparticles is the combination of CE and Free flow electrophoresis (FFE) approaches [18]. High-sensitivity analysis, micro preparative separation, and isolation of biomolecules and bioparticles at the picomole to nanomole (nanogram-microgram) level are all made feasible by CE methods. The appropriate CE separation conditions may be translated from capillary microscale into (macro)preparative FFE format with the preparative capacity of tens to hundreds of milligrams of substances per hour based on a direct correlation between CE and FFE procedures. Three different amino acid mixtures were separated using a unique electrophoresis method called Nafion membrane electrophoresis [19]. Narrow hydrophilic holes (10–60 μm) for mass transfer, the absence of any liquid solution visible in the separation column, a low operating voltage, and straightforward detection are only a few benefits offered by Nafion membrane electrophoresis. Additional research will focus on the separation mechanism, the requirement to reduce the Joule heating to provide better temperature management of the separating columns, and the need to reduce the elution time to produce sharper peaks in the patterns and enhance separation efficiency [19].

The reversible molecular interactions that are essential to the operation of all biological systems are largely unresolved, and the affinity electrophoretic techniques represent an important subfield that will continue to be spread throughout biomolecular science and make significant contributions in this regard [20]. It has been shown that the electrophoretic process causes the temperature to rise unevenly in various parts of the electrophoretic chamber [21]. Temperature rise might reach 5–7°C in the tank utilized. Differences in heating in various sections of the solution at different time intervals are explained by

convective processes, the arrangement of the electrophoretic chamber, and a change in the conductivity of the solution. It is preferable to rule out the potential of gas bubbles created on the electrodes spreading into the region of the electrophoretic platform to lessen the influence of convection. The electrophoretic chamber's center is often where the most heating occurs. Identical to the temperature on the surface of the solution after the conclusion of electrophoresis, the temperature of the slides is also similar. The distribution of temperature rise in any other electrophoretic chamber is very difficult to predict. Similar thermal imaging methods might be utilized to produce accurate findings for different kinds of electrophoretic chambers [21].

A separation method called dual-opposite injection capillary electrophoresis combines injection from both ends of the capillary with a suppressed electroosmotic flow to study cations and anions concurrently in one run [22]. When addressing DOI-CE, some articles don't present a whole picture and occasionally skip over the positive aspects that make it a workable method of separation. Only three surfactants (CTAC, DMDOAB, and SDS) were shown to be efficient when eight ionic surfactants were used to investigate the separation of synthetic polymers. The choice of ionic surfactant is crucial for the NACZE polymer separation process, and it appears that cationic species are more suited than anionic ones as an addition. Our research showed that the hydrophobic interaction between the polymer and the ionic surfactant is what mostly drives the NACZE separation of the polymers. Additionally, it was implied from PC's electrophoretic behavior that the electrostatic force also influences the contact.

The hydrophobic interactions between polymers and surfactants will be strengthened as the concentration of the comparatively polar solvent in the electrophoretic medium, will be useful for the separation of the polymers [23]. Polar mixes have been shown to have unstable electrophoretic activity, making them largely ineffective for solving neutral synthetic polymers. Therefore, for the polymer separation in NACE, the use of more hydrophobic ionic species, such as specific ionic liquids, will be effective. Additionally, we hypothesized that the hydrophobic cationic species is appropriate for polymer separation. As a result, our laboratory is now doing research on NACZE employing ionic liquid to separate synthetic linear polymers [23].

1.2 Problem Statement

According to [24], molecular-based technologies for blood type genotyping are currently labor- and time-intensive and poorly suited to clinical circumstances requiring immediate transfusion. According to the modeling of soft particle electrophoresis [2]. For instance, discussions about concentrated suspensions are only possible using the outdated traditional cell model. However, the surface adsorption of particles on the border, particle mobility in regions other than the channel axis, and particle interaction in the microchannel have not yet been studied in capillary electrophoresis models. Recent research suggests that some bio-species cores may be deemed electrolyte permeable. Electrophoretic mobility might rise as a result of such a factor. Particle deformation is another newly discovered area of interest that has lately been brought forward by certain researchers [9]. As a result of electric force, hydrodynamic drag, or fluid structural interaction, which is a recent field of study on the particle electrophoresis that impacts the particle inertia, development of EDL, and subsequent distributions of the charge throughout the particle, the particle may deform in reality [9]. Due to the two-way nature of the fluid-structure interaction, the deformation of the particles has a sizable impact on the flow field surrounding them [6].

Up to now, only electrophoresis of either hard particles or soft particles without cores has addressed this new challenge [7], [9]. In the current study, measurements of electrophoretic mobility at varied bulk ionic concentrations were used to develop a technique for concurrently determining the zeta potential and slip coefficient of micro and nanoparticles. As long as the measurement error is sufficiently managed, it is discovered that the current approach produces predictions that are quite accurate. According to [4], resistors were not used in the construction of electrophoresis. But today's electrophoresis machines have evolved into sophisticated tools that can separate blood and categorize it into categories, such as AA, AS, and SS, thanks to advancements in electronic chips. Furthermore, huge plastic or metallic cubes are frequently used in electrophoresis locally. The plastic will be cut into two cubic boxes, one of which will serve as the tank and the other as the engine, creating a separation that will separate the two components. According to [15] the PEL has pH-dependent charge characteristics because zwitterionic functional groups are present. The ion partitioning effect was caused by the assumption that the dielectric permittivity of the PEL and bulk aqueous media was different. To investigate the fundamentals of electrokinetic separations and provide insights into the behavior of buffer systems and sample components of all electrophoretic separation techniques, such as moving boundary electrophoresis, CZE, CGE, ITP, IEF, EKC, ACE, and CEC, the dynamic models are the most flexible tools available [16]. Additionally, the electrophoretic medium's increased concentration of the comparatively polar solvent will strengthen the hydrophobic interactions between the surfactants and the polymers, which will be useful for polymer separation [23]. According to Als, only three surfactants (CTAC, DMDOAB, and SDS) were successful in separating the synthetic polymers when eight ionic surfactants were used. To increase sensitivity, the detection electrode should be adjusted, for as by lowering the dead volume [19]. Both the CE and the FFE procedures have the benefit of being carried out in mild carrier-less free-solution media, which minimizes the losses of separated biomolecules and bioparticles and maintains their biological activity [18]. According to [19], amino acids lack a distinctive chromophore or fluorescence that would allow for quick and direct detection. This makes amino acid analysis and detection extremely difficult. According to [22], the most typical misconceptions about DOI-CE are that it is difficult to avoid co-detection between analytes that have opposite charges, that separation cannot be completed using standard capillary zone electrophoresis (CZE) equipment, and that the detector needs to be moved to a central location for the separation to take place. The supposed difficulty of choosing an acceptable background electrolyte and the incompatibility of various sample introduction techniques with DOI-CE are further, less widespread fallacies.

2 Literature Review

2.1 History of Electrophoresis

Electrophoresis is the movement of dispersed molecules or particles in a sample concerning a fluid under the influence of an electric field [25], [26]. This method is often used to separate or purify macromolecules based on their size and charge, especially proteins and nucleic acids, in a variety of applications [27]. Additionally, this electrokinetic method has advanced significantly and is continuously being explored, according to [27]. This method works by giving molecules like deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA), ribonucleic acid (RNA), and proteins a negative charge that causes them to move toward a positive charge. Following the separation of these compounds, a picture of the gel is taken, producing a picture of the gel that shows

a visual depiction of the molecular fragments that have been separated. So, electrophoresis, a powerful and affordable molecular separation technique, is a purification approach with little sample demand and great resolution, according to [28].

For more than a century, researchers have known that proteins and enzymes may move in an electric field. However, it wasn't until Arne Tiselius demonstrated that serum proteins could be separated by electrophoresis in the late 1930s that this phenomenon was used to regular chemical separations. The method was the initial practical use of electrophoresis in medical research and was awarded the 1948 Nobel Prize in Chemistry. The apparatus used by Tiselius for these tests included a U-shaped tube into which he placed his sample and a flowing buffer. When an electric field was applied across the tube, the sample proteins started to separate based on their charge and size. The proteins in the sample started to separate according to their charge and size as they went toward the electrode with the opposite charge. The outcome was a collection of broad, only partially resolved bands, which were then used to determine the protein content of the sample. Tiselius' method is currently referred to as "moving boundary electrophoresis" as a result of the fact that it produced a series of shifting borders, as seen in the figure below, between those regions that contained unique protein combinations [29].

Figure 1: Electrophoresis-Ion-Binding

To enable analytes to be separated into narrow bands or zones, it is increasingly customary in modern labs to use more effective separation methods and a little amount of material. These conditions have led to the development of a technique known as "zone electrophoresis." Although Tiselius employed an open tube method, gels or other supports eventually replaced open tubes as the preferred format for electrophoresis in clinical labs for over 50 years. Because it needed fewer samples, was simpler to operate, and offered more reliability in performing separations, gel or paper electrophoresis was chosen at this time over large open tubes filled with flowing buffer. The development of superior separation supports, including polyacrylamide gels, as well as the introduction of novel gel electrophoresis-based techniques have increased the appeal of gel electrophoresis in particular. Still used in clinical and biological laboratories are sodium dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) and isoelectric focusing (IEF) [29].

The electrophoresis method was at first crude. To get to where it is now, it underwent several alterations after that. In the meanwhile, several things have happened that have influenced the development of various electrophoresis techniques. Today, every electrophoretic method variant is appropriate and specifically designed for a single purpose. The kind of approach may be chosen based on the price and applicability.

Gels for sequencing were first employed in 1977. After detection, the sequence was read in the lanes from the bottom of the gel to the top. To resolve single-stranded biomolecules, it is utilized. Agarose gel electrophoresis was created in 1979. Pulsed-field electrophoresis was created in 1983. It is used to separate bigger molecules with a 12Mb size. Greater molecular movement occurs as a result of applying pulses for longer periods. The capillary electrophoresis method was used in 1983.

2.1.1 Electrophoresis Methods

Zone and moving boundary electrophoresis are the two most used forms of electrophoresis. Zone electrophoresis is the movement of charged molecules in a solution with the supporting medium. The divided components in the supporting medium create distinct zones. A little quantity of sample is applied in the form of a narrow band after the supporting medium has been saturated with buffer solution. Moving boundary electrophoresis studies, the motion of charged molecules in a free-moving solution without the aid of a supporting medium. Paper electrophoresis, thin-layer electrophoresis, gel electrophoresis, and cellulose acetate electrophoresis are examples of zone electrophoresis. The many forms of moving boundary electrophoresis include capillary electrophoresis (CE), isoelectric focusing, isotachopheresis, and immunoelectrophoresis.

2.1.2 Zone Electrophoresis

The separation of amino acids by electrophoresis in a thin layer of silica or alumina is known as electrophoresis with thin layers.

2.1.3 Cellulose acetate electrophoresis

Paper electrophoresis has been modified by cellulose acetate electrophoresis. Acetic acid and cotton are combined to create cellulose acetate, which is then produced by accelerating the process using sulfuric acid. Filter paper is used to facilitate the migration of the sample in the buffer on the cellulose surface plate based on the charge.

2.1.4 Electrophoresis of paper

Whatman no. 1 and Whatman no. 3 filter paper is utilized as a support medium. This technique makes use of paper that is 5 cm broad. It might take up to 16 to 18 hours to complete the molecular separation process. Two troughs are part of the apparatus; one of them is used to transmit electric current through, while the other one holds a buffer solution. As seen in figure 2, a distinct band of molecules migrates as a homogenous group of molecules. A fixative, such as acetone or methanol, is used to attach separated molecules to a solid substrate. This method was used to determine the stability constants of cobalt (II) and beryllium (II) metal perchlorate complexes at various pH values [30]. Also presented is the use of an ionophoretic for the analysis of compounds of biological significance [31]. Electrophoresis in starch gel or

agar was nonetheless introduced as a result of its drawbacks, such as a long period and indistinct edges [27].

2.1.6 Electrophoresis of Gel

The molecular sieving method is used to separate molecules and is based on the molecular sieve of the substances. A colloid that functions as a molecular sieve is called a molecular sieve. The conductivity should be neutral. Agarose, polyacrylamide, starch, and Sephadex are examples of gel materials. The gel simultaneously allows smaller molecules to flow through while impeding the movement of bigger ones.

A pure, uncharged carbohydrate obtained from seaweed is called agarose. It has repeating units of 3,6-anhydrous-L-galactose. Agarose stays liquid when added to a boiling liquid until it reaches a temperature of 40°C. The gel state develops when the temperature is further lowered. By varying the amount of agarose in the gel, the pore size may be altered. Agarose gel is created by weak hydrogen and hydrophobic bonds, which makes the molecule fragile. It is affected by the size of the DNA molecule, the amount of agarose, the conformation of the DNA, the voltage used, the presence of ethidium bromide, the types of agarose, and the electrophoresis buffer [32].

2.1.7 Starch

It is created by boiling a suspension of granular starch in a buffer until it solidifies as a colloid. The branching amylopectin chains lead the colloid to cool and solidify into a semi-solid gel. The skin is covered in petroleum jelly to prevent edema and shrinkage.

2.1.8 Acrylic Acid Gel

A polyacrylamide gel is created when acrylamide is polymerized in the presence of the crosslinking agent methylene-bis-acrylamide. Covalent cross-links are used to bind acrylamide monomers together. It is inert, thermostable, strong, and transparent, and it is more resilient than an agarose gel. It is uncharged and available in a variety of pore sizes. Protein molecules can be differentiated based on their charge-to-mass ratio and molecular size.

2.1.9 Gel made with native polyacrylamide

The natural structure of the analyte is maintained since it is conducted under non-denaturing circumstances. To distinguish between molecules, consider their sizes, shapes, and charges. It is the original method and is referred to as native polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (PAGE). It facilitates the separation or purification of a protein mixture.

2.1.1 Denatured polyacrylamide gel or sodium dodecyl sulfate gel (SDS-PAGE)

This approach is frequently used to determine the molecular weight of proteins. The samples are divided using electrophoretic mobility and molecular weight. PAGE is known as SDS PAGE because SDS detergent is applied to it. SDS maintained a constant mass-charge ratio through protein coverage. Proteins move in ascending sequences of increasing molecular weights or sizes. Non-sulfide-lined secondary and tertiary structures are removed when proteins are treated with SDS, which imparts a negative charge proportionate to their length. Molecules with a wide pH range will thus have a net negative charge. When

proteins bind to SDS, charge densities are formed, and they separate based on mass as shown in figure 3 below.

2.2 Movement-Based Electrophoresis

2.2.1 Isotachopheresis

Isotachopheresis is defined as the movement occurring at the same pace. The development of potential gradients is an issue. Both leading and trailing electrolytes are used in electrolytes. While the subsequent electrolyte moves more slowly than the slowest sample, the leading electrolyte moves quicker than the fastest sample. The leading electrolyte migrates quickly towards the associated electrode after the application of voltage, followed by the sample ions, generating zones in the order of mobilities.

By utilizing isoelectric focusing, pH gradients may be created. Each protein is transferred to a pH-regulated area. Protein bands are clearly defined and crisp because the pH of the gradient and the protein are the same. Migration occurs over a certain distance depending on the isoelectric point. The protein's net charge drops to zero when migration is stopped, and zwitterion is created. When the pH of the solution drops below the protein, the protein becomes positively charged and moves in the direction of the cathode. When the pH of the solution is higher than the pH of the protein, the protein becomes negatively charged and moves toward the anode. Since the electrolyte has aliphatic amino groups and carboxylic acid groups with various isoelectric properties, it is an ampholyte.

2.2.2 Immunoelectrophoresis

When an electric current is applied to a slide covered in a layer of gel, a mixture of antigens contained in the wells is divided into individual antigens based on size and charge. After that, certain antisera that have been positioned in troughs parallel to the electrophoretic migration and diffusion are permitted to react with the separated molecules. Antisera in the troughs move in the direction of the antigens, interact with them, and produce unique precipitin lines, showing that specific proteins elicit an antibody response.

Figure 2: Filter-paper electrophoresis outline

Figure 3: Disc-Gel electrophoresis.

Figure 4: Applications for CE in the realm of clinical chemistry [33]

2.2.3 Capillary Electrophoresis (CE)

Capillary electrophoresis is the process of separating molecules by filling capillaries with buffers and applying high voltages. The internal diameter of the capillaries, which ranges from 25 to 100 nanometers, is modest. The increased resolution, sensitivity, and online detection are made possible by filling the capillaries with a gel, which prevents electro-osmotic flow. The method is carried out identically to classical electrophoresis. Electrodes are also inserted into the reservoirs to complete the circuit.

2.2.4. Review of related works

The Capillary electrophoresis technique provides several benefits, including quick speed, effective separation, and a wide analytical scope, according to a review of relevant research [26], [34]. Contrarily, CE usually exhibits low concentration sensitivity and limited tolerance for matrix components, necessitating sample preparation before separation and detection., capillary electrophoresis is a continually developing analytical method used for a variety of applications [35]. The bulk of the problems with this method, notably the adsorption process, have also been eliminated by the advancement of conventional capillary electrophoresis through the use of new coated capillaries. The purpose of CE was to be downsized and utilized in microfluidic devices. Microfluidic CE devices enable separation and detection when used in combination with a conventional detection system like MS. When it comes to complex sample analysis, CE has shown to be a very versatile separation technique with a lot of promise. The most promising field for progress is microfluidic CE development using inventive surface microchannel modification and online connectivity to advanced sensing systems. Nonetheless, more study is still needed in this area.

In a similar manner to the current trend in column coating for capillary electrophoresis, [36] found out that, Capillary coatings effectively improve the separation performance of proteins in capillary electrophoresis, primarily by reducing protein adsorption onto the inner capillary wall and by regulating the electroosmotic flow (EOF) to accommodate the separation problem in hand. Nanomaterials have great potential for capillary coating preparations due to their advantageous properties, such as high surface-to-volume ratios and a broad range of chemical options.

Serum and urine protein electrophoresis is not a common screening technique. They are used to check for M proteins in those who could have problems in the proliferation of B-lymphocytes or plasma cells. However, serum and urine protein electrophoresis typically detects a wide range of other aberrations in addition to M proteins that, as mentioned above, may provide valuable clinical information. Therefore, it is necessary to check every section of the electrophoretic pattern, and any irregularities should be documented in the final report [34].

According to [37], the requirement for analytical techniques that can handle samples with complex matrices and/or identify several unique chemicals in a single run has increased, which has led to the development of multidimensional separation techniques. The effectiveness of separation can be increased by including a second dimension, particularly one that is highly orthogonal to the first. This also makes it possible to use CE separation techniques with electrolytes that are incompatible with ESI in the first dimension. There has been a lot of interest in the development of online two-dimensional chromatographic separation systems. Two-dimensional gas or liquid chromatography is more straightforward than using two-dimensional capillary electrophoresis because of the ease of using high voltages and volume transfers in the nanoliter range, but two-dimensional capillary electrophoresis is more difficult to handle high voltages and volume transfers in the nanoliter range. Effective 2D interfacing for online 2D separations of capillary electromigration methods is therefore a very recent research field.

3 Methodology

The development process included a five-stage Design thinking model proposed by the Hasso-Plattner Institute of Design at Stanford (d. school) [22].

- a) Empathize
- b) Define
- c) Ideate
- d) Prototype
- e) Test

The primary data were collected from the medical practitioners on how existing electrophoresis machines used in the facility could be improved. Secondly, research was done to structurally define the problem statement. Brainstorming was further done to generate innovative solutions after which a final design concept was settled on. **Figure 9** shows the block diagram of the project and **figure 14** depicts the overall design operational circuit diagram.

Other approaches used for the design are the Systemic method for system development, Circuit Analysis, and the use of proteus to simulate the circuit of the hardware design.

The device comprised a 1.5KW transformer, a regulator, a timer relay, and an alarm system. It is capable to evaluate the genotype of humans by using blood as a sample under an electric current within a few minutes. the device contains three tank outputs which make it the capacity to accommodate three different sample tanks and the test can be run simultaneously, the device is smarter enough to raise an alarm when the test process is completed.

3.1 Procedure

Time is firstly set, when the circuit is powered by the closing switch, then the timer relay power the transformer, and the four tags diode converts A.C current to D.C current. The voltage from the D.C. output still contains some degree of ripples. These ripples are further removed by the capacitor through the current flow through the transformer. This is a better D.C output but not free of ripples. It is then fed to the voltage regulator which not just reduces the final output of the power supply but also keeps it constant which is now suitable for the proper operation of the tank. The resistors work with the regulator [switches to regulate voltage flowing into the tank].

The output is connected to the tank energies for separation in the tank. (Separation of blood samples in the tank). When the process is completed, the relay timer de-energizes the transformer and opens for the buzzer to raise an alarm.

3.2 The Design Equations

To completely understand the separation of charged particles in electrophoresis, it is important to look at some simple equations relating to electrophoresis. When the potential difference (voltage) is applied across the electrodes, it generates a potential gradient (E), which is the applied voltage (v) divided by the distance (d) between the electrodes.

$$E = \frac{v}{d} \quad (1)$$

When the potential gradient E is applied, the Force on a molecule bearing a charge of q coulombs is Eq . (newtons).

$$F = Eq \quad (2)$$

where F is the force that drives a charged molecule toward an electrode.

There is also a frictional resistance that slows down the movement of this charged molecule. The frictional force is a measure of the hydrodynamic size of the molecule, the shape of the molecule, the pore size of the medium in which electrophoresis is taking place, and the viscosity of the buffer. The velocity (v) of a charged molecule in an electric field is given by the equation.

$$V = fq \quad (3)$$

Where f is the frictional coefficient.

In electrophoresis, the force moving the micro molecule (nucleic acids or proteins) is the electrical potential, E . The electrophoresis mobility of an ion is the ratio of the velocity of the particle, (v) to the electrical potential.

$$E_m = \frac{V}{E} \quad (4)$$

Electrophoresis mobility is also equal to the net charge of the molecule, Z divided by the frictional coefficient,

$$F = \frac{Z}{f} \quad (5)$$

When a potential difference is applied, molecules with different overall charges will begin to separate due to their different electrophoresis mobilities. Even molecules with similar charges will begin to separate if they have different molecular sizes. Since they will experience different frictional forces.

The current in a solution between the electrodes is conducted mainly by the buffer ions with a small proportion being conducted by the sample ions. Ohm's law expresses the relationship between current (I), voltage (V), and resistance (R).

$$V = IR \quad (6)$$

This equation demonstrates that it is possible to accelerate an electrophoretic separation by increasing the applied voltage, which would result in a corresponding increase in the current flow. The distance migrated will be proportional to both current and time. However, increasing the voltage would ignore one of the major problems for most forms of electrophoresis, namely the generation of heat. During electrophoresis, the power P (in watts,) generated in the supporting medium is given by:

$$P = I^2R \quad (7)$$

The power supply is attached to the sample tank, the timer is set, and the machine starts up. The buzzer will sound an alarm to notify the user that the test procedure is finished when the time limit has passed.

3.3 Computer-Aided Design

This shows the design from a different perspective of view, like The Front View, The Side View, The Top View, and the Back View

The Front View displays the three-tank output of the device power supply, switch, power cable, and the AV cable connected to the AV male port of the sample tank as it is shown in figure 5 below.

The Side View revealed the inner part of the sample tank which is very important, there is segregation between the anode and the cathode which prevents bridging before the test start-up as it is shown in figure 6 below.

The Top View showcases the timer relay, indicators, and regulator as it is shown in figure 7 below.

Finally, the Back view shows the power cable of the device and the back of the sample tank as it is shown in figure 8 below.

Figure 5: Front View

Figure 6: Side View

Figure 7: Top View

Figure 8: Rear View

Figure 9: Block Diagram of the system (Electrophoresis Machine)

The Sample Tank

Figure 12: Sample tank

Figure 13: Developed Electrophoresis Machine

The tank is made up of plastic, and it contains the anode and the cathode terminals in which platinum wire is used as a source of the electrodes that conduct current into the buffer solution in the tank. The

content of the tank includes; The Buffer solution [tris] of 8.7ph, Filter paper, Cellulose acetate paper, and platinum wire which serves as the electrode.

Operational ALGORITHM

This is the conceptualization of the project and the actual performance of the project in an orderly manner;

- i Start
- ii The burden to solve a problem
- iii Identifying the problem
- iv Defining the problem
- v Proffering a solution
- vi Solution design state
- vii Segmenting of the various solutions into units
- viii Identification of the various components
- ix Designing the various units
- x Testing
- xi Documentation
- xii End

ELECTROPHORESIS CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

Time is firstly set (Timer Relay) when the circuit is powered by a closing switch (SW1), then the timer relay power the transformer (Step-up), at the output of the transformer, a switch is utilized to switch the output voltage to either High/Low, depending on the amount of input voltage coming from the source. The regulator (variable), also controls the incoming current before flowing into the transformer, the four tags diode (Bridge wave) at the control unit stage, converts A.C current to D.C current. The voltage from the D.C. output still contains some degree of ripples. These ripples are further removed by the capacitor, through the current flow through the transformer. This is a better D.C output but not free of ripples.

Figure 14: Electrophoresis circuit design

Two electrolytic capacitors were connected in parallel to boost the DC output. It is then fed to the voltage regulator which not just reduces the final output of the power supply but also keeps it constant which is now suitable for the proper operation of the tank. The resistors work with the regulator [switches to regulate voltage flowing into the tank]. The output is connected to the tank energies for separation in the tank. (Separation of blood samples in the tank). When the process is completed, the relay timer de-energizes the transformer and opens for the buzzer to raise an alarm.

4 A new optimized ranking algorithm

4.1 Design Testing and Results

After the completion of this design, each unit was tested to ensure the proper operation of the device. The expected output voltage, current, power, and frequency were measured using a multi-meter, wattmeter, and frequency counter.

4.1.2 Sample Tank evaluation (Control and Unknown samples)

The device was tested to evaluate blood genotype, a blood sample was collected from five different individuals in four different categories and A S was utilized as the control. The key factor is [AS blood sample]. The electrode (platinum wire) is placed in a tank containing 8.7 pH Tris buffer, which is then filled with cellulose acetate paper and let to soak for at least 10 minutes. To prevent the buffer from soaking up too much, acetate paper has to be cleaned. Unknown blood samples will be arranged in a straight line with the control [A S]. From the positive to the negative terminal, the sample moves. The A S sample and the unknown sample will be arranged linearly on top of the cellulose acetate paper. The 'S' migrates more quickly than the 'A', which is the deciding factor, during the separation from the positive to the negative pole that occurs when the machine is energized. It is necessary to account for how unknown sample migration.

The genotype is AA if the unidentified samples are below the A band. The genotype is SS if the unidentified sample is below the S-band, and AS if it is below both the A and S bands.

The flow of negative and positive current in the tank will be enabled by the circuit's current, separating the samples.

Figure 15: Tank analysis (Control and Unknown Samples)

The device was confirmed functioning normally after carrying out the test using a blood sample and the result is shown below.

Figure 16: The Blood Separation on Cellulose Acetate Paper

4.2 Results Tabulation

CATEGORY I

S/N	Blood Sample	Genotype
1.	Control	AS
2.	Unknown Sample A	AA
3.	Unknown Sample B	AA
4.	Unknown Sample C	AS
5.	Unknown Sample D	AS
6.	Unknown Sample E	AS

Table I Result: AA = 2, AS = 3, SS = 0

CATEGORY II

S/N	Blood Sample	Genotype
1.	Control	AS
2.	Unknown Sample A	AS
3.	Unknown Sample B	AS
4.	Unknown Sample C	AS
5.	Unknown Sample D	AS
6.	Unknown Sample E	AA

Table II: Result: AA = 1, AS = 4, SS = 0

CATEGORY III

S/N	Blood Sample	Genotype
1.	Control	AS
2.	Unknown Sample A	SS
3.	Unknown Sample B	AA
4.	Unknown Sample C	AA
5.	Unknown Sample D	AS
6.	Unknown Sample E	AS

Table III: Result: AA = 2, AS = 2, SS = 1

CATEGORY IV

S/N	Blood Sample	Genotype
1.	Control	AS
2.	Unknown Sample A	AA
3.	Unknown Sample B	AS
4.	Unknown Sample C	AS
5.	Unknown Sample D	SS
6.	Unknown Sample E	AA

Table IV: Result: AA = 2, AS = 2, SS = 1

CHARTS

Figure 17: The Results Column Chart

Figure 18: The Results Pie Chart

This chart shows the results of the blood samples collected from the First Technical University Medical Center. The blood samples were collected from five different people of an unknown genotype while a known genotype blood sample (AS) was collected to make it six these serves as the control sample as it was shown tables III and IV above. The samples were taken from five different sets of students and grouped into four categories, while the control sample remains and was used as the base control for each category as shown on tables I-IV above.

After completing the test using the developed device, the result was taken and recorded, tabulated and the number of AA, AS, and SS genotypes were recorded for each category as it was shown above. Then the chart above represents the total number of AA, AS, and SS blood genotypes recorded from the tables. The blood samples category was plotted against the genotype frequency as it was shown in the figure17 above.

The pie chart above shows the result of the total number of AA, AS and SS blood from the entire test carried out from different categories. The blue area represents the grey blood type and which is just 2 which is 10% of the entire chart, while the blue area represents the AA blood type which is 7in number and 35% of the chart lastly the orange area represents the AS blood type and are 11 which 55% of the chart as it all shown in figure 18 above, compared with other conventional devices, this is seeming to be more effective, accurate, fast and safe to use.

5 Conclusion

While performing the genotyping procedure, the ability to run multiple procedures at a stretch would save cost, time, and energy. A specialized electrophoretic technician can routinely run about 10 gels per day with a hands-on power supply or constant vigilance to maintain a time of less than 5 h per day, unlike most conventional electrophoresis machines with only one or two sample tanks, this system has three sample tanks, which can accommodate multiple samples at a stretch. The low-cost smart electrophoresis machine would be beneficial for low-earning income hospitals compared to most conventional electrophoresis machine that requires close monitoring when in use, this design will not require

operational monitoring for it has an automated time relay breaker which automatically triggers off the test process once it is completed.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

We declare that we have no conflicts of interest.

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